

ABSTRACT

Geography is one of the essential secondary school subjects. Geography is a distinct and dynamic field of science and social science that studies man and his physical surroundings. This quasi-experimental research utilized a one-group, pretest-posttest method to assess students' academic performance when educational technology is integrated into their academic endeavors. The results of this study indicate that students got an average level of academic performance during the pre-test when the traditional method was used. Moreover, when Earth Science Puzzle was integrated as part of the treatment, the students scored high; thus, data suggest that Earth Science Puzzle is an effective educational technology device when maximized in the classroom compared to the traditional method.

Keywords: *Earth Science Puzzle, quasi-experimental, Teaching Geography, Social Sciences*

INTRODUCTION

Geography is one of the essential secondary school subjects (Firth, 2011). Geography is a distinct and dynamic field of science and social science that studies man and his physical surroundings (Akintade, 2012). Geography is a distinct and dynamic field of science and social science that studies man and his physical surroundings (Akintade, 2012).

According to recent studies (Dummer et al., 2008; Healey, 2005; Mangan et al., 2010), the number of students choosing to study Geography in Malaysian upper secondary schools and their degree of achievement in the subject has decreased. The most significant factor is a lack of motivation. As a result, Malaysian upper secondary school students are now skipping Geography. Furthermore, the number of surviving students who continue to study Geography and pass the exam is decreasing year after year. According to (Singh et al., 2013), the main factor contributing to this problem is that Malaysian students need to be more motivated to study geography and increasingly perceive it as a dry subject with few opportunities to use technology.

Traditional teaching methods are distinguished by using pendulums, chalkboards, and pencils for writing (Koehler & Mishra, 2014). Teaching and learning with these are straightforward in terms of their functions (Lim et al., 2013). Butzin (2014) defines traditional education as the availability of processes and practices established to maintain a conducive environment in which the educational process can impact. Educational technology, broadly defined as hardware and software that support educational goals, is a method of instruction introduced previously. Laptop computers are now frequently included in schools. Chromebooks, iPads and other tablets, smartphones, and intelligent whiteboards are all options. (Delgado et al, 2015).

Today's students have grown up in a technologically advanced society and are enthusiastic and capable of utilizing it (Derbel, 2017; Prensky, 2010). This technologically sophisticated generation's learning demands and requirements have developed dramatically over time (Cameron, 2005; Lai & Hong, 2015).

There are numerous ways to incorporate technology into classrooms to create a technologically enhanced learning environment—for instance, the integration of the Jigsaw Puzzle Application. The jigsaw puzzle app will become an essential educational tool in the classroom. It allows students to learn, cooperate, and share ideas using their smartphones. (Gumbao, 2021)

The 21st century has changed how geography is taught and shaped as a means of technology overview. As new technology becomes available, so do new methods of teaching geography in high schools (Liu et al., 2012). The use of technology in the classroom has contributed to the advancement of teachers' instructional skills, resulting in advancements in the drafting of teaching lessons, acquiring knowledge, and advancing classroom communication with students (Cuban et al., 2011).

According to Koehler and Mishra (2017), traditional teaching methods have been around for a long time with little development. In contrast, the advancement of technology-integrated education has significantly grown teachers' instructing skills and abilities, thereby improving educational quality. The same study by Koehler & Mishra (2017) revealed that the use of technology in education had reduced the exhaustion and burnout that results from the traditional mode of instructing and learning by providing an encouraging learning environment for students due to the variety of knowledge content expressed by technology.

The researcher has observed that technology is essential in catching students' attention. One study has concluded that students' attention spans have become shorter than they used to (Bradbury, 2016). Therefore, we need to investigate the impact of integrating educational technology into our teaching practices.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This quasi-experimental research utilized a one-group, pretest-posttest method to assess students' academic performance when educational technology is integrated into their academic endeavors. This design is the most suitable for this study since it aims to examine the effect of the Traditional Method and Earth Science Puzzle on the academic performance of geography students at Banate National High School.

Respondents. The respondents of this study are the Grade Seven students of Banate National High School enrolled for the school year 2022-2023. A total of 60 high school students actively participated in this study.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher submitted a letter to the office of the principal of Banate National High School, asking permission to conduct the study in the seventh-grade department with their selected students as respondents. Afterward, a communication letter was sent to the cooperating seventh-grade teacher as a sign of courtesy and asking for the teacher's permission to conduct a study. The lesson plan, table of specifications, and two sets of multiple-choice exams were given to the cooperating teacher. At the first meeting, the subject teacher taught using traditional methods and provided a pre-test. After a 3-week lapse, the same topic was conducted again, using the Earth Science Puzzle, and a post-test exam was given after the intervention.

The cooperating teacher presented five map-like jigsaw puzzles for the students to solve. The puzzle is made up of images from the lesson. Each puzzle has been judged and will be solved when the participant places each piece on the laptop in the correct location so that all parts are joined along the correct boundaries.

Fig. 1 shows the cellular phone screen that displays the program.

The puzzle screen will show this image if the learners press the green button to begin the program, whereas the blue button is used if the teacher wants the learners to puzzle out other images.

Fig. 2 shows the cellular phone screen of the first completed puzzle application.

The puzzle pieces are arranged in two columns, with the pictures cut into jigsaw puzzle pieces on the left side and the exact location of each puzzle piece on the right. The learner will drag each puzzle piece to the right side of the program window. By tapping the puzzle pieces, you can rotate them. The program would only be completed if the learner attempted to leave a piece in the correct location.

When all puzzle pieces are correctly placed, the program will display an on-screen message confirming that the puzzle has been solved (see Illustration 3). The participant will move on to the next puzzle.

Fig. 3 shows the cellular phone screen of the first completed puzzle application.

Data Analysis Procedure. Using the paired sample t-test to compare the means of two measurements taken from the same person, object, or measuring unit. The measurement will be performed at two points in time, the pre-test and post-test scores, with the intervention in between. The pre-test and post-test results provided the data required to describe the students' performance exposed to the Earth Science Puzzle. The learners' performance on the pre-test and post-test was described as follows: 0-5.99= low, 6-10.99= average, and 11-15= high.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that students got an average score when taken as a whole ($m = 10.0$, $SD = 2.06$). The result suggests that the traditional teaching method is effective at the average level, as reflected by the academic performance of grade seven students. Moreover, the data may imply that seventh-grade students are accustomed to the traditional method of instruction, which may be attributed to the students' diverse learning styles, attention spans, and individual differences.

According to the study (Bradbury, 2016), student attention is high at the start of a lecture; it reaches a low point after 10–15 minutes. Most students pay attention as the lecture starts, and for most of them, that attention span lasts around 10 minutes.

Table 2 shows as a whole ($m = 13.4$, $SD = 1.21$), which is interpreted as high. The result suggests that using the Earth Science Puzzle is an effective method when utilized in the classroom. The data may imply that the academic performance of seventh-grade students is high when using educational technology as the mode of teaching.

The outcome of this recent study was in favor of the statement of Heafner (2004); technology allows students to search for and get material quickly, and it has "assisted them in understanding what they were talking about in class." The intervention may contribute to the learning taking place in class. They are pleased to provide their time and technological expertise. Students are also at ease when using technology and completing activities. Students' confidence helps them build motivation for their learning.

Another study by Shivakumar and Manichander (2013) explores education in the twenty-first century and how technology may be a valuable tool for students. They stressed collaboration, the use of blended learning, and information and communication technologies (ICT). Teachers can learn about technology and some issues that arise while using ICT.

Table 1&2. Academic Performance of Grade Seven Students

Traditional Method	M	N	SD	Interpretation
	10.0	60	2.06	Average
Earth Science Puzzle	13.4	60	1.21	High

Table 3 shows a statistical difference in the result of the Pre-test and Post-test when using Earth Science Puzzle with the $m = -3.43$; $SD = 2.15$; $t = -12.37$; $t = -12.369$; $df = 59$; $p < .000$.

As shown in the table, educational technology is more effective than the traditional method when utilized as a medium of instruction. This study is supported by a study (Hennessy et al., 2015) that also emphasized the necessity to improve the traditional chalk-and-talk method to accommodate the changing preferences of students in the modern age group. The use of technology in education expands educational opportunities and fields since it may be used on a large scale, which relieves stress associated with the use of large classes (Lim et al., 2013).

Table 3. The difference in the Traditional Method and Earth Science Puzzle

Traditional Method –	M	SD	t	p-value
Earth Science Puzzle	-3.433	2.150	-12.37	0.000

Note: The difference in the means is significant when $p \leq 0.05$

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of data gathered, the researcher was successful in determining the effectiveness of the traditional method and the Earth Science Puzzle and discovered that there is a significant difference between the traditional method and Earth Science Puzzle and that the Earth Science Puzzle (ESP) can be successfully utilized to teach geography and that ESP improved the academic performance of Banate National High School grade seven students. As a result, traditional teaching methods such as demonstrations and discussions only succeed at an average level. Therefore, educational technology should be incorporated into the lecturer's lesson plan. Educational technology alone cannot lead to successful learning; however, with the teacher's active involvement. Teachers should take advantage of the motivational effect of educational technology and use it more often. Moreover, future research could concentrate on using educational technology in specific topic teaching, classroom management, and the specific components that increase motivation, learning attainment, and achievement.

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